

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik**

CyberKnife® SBRT of breast cancer – clinical aspects

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Stereotactic accelerated partial breast irradiation (SAPBI) is a targeted radiotherapy method for treating early-stage breast cancer as an alternative to whole breast irradiation (WBI). SAPBI using a robotic stereotactic radiation therapy system (CyberKnife®; CK) is an emerging, non-invasive technique characterized by its unique beam arrangements and real-time motion tracking. The aim of this presentation is to summarize the outcomes of studies using CK-based SAPBI, and present the experience of the National Institute of Oncology (NIO), Budapest.

Clinical studies have shown comparable local tumor control and survival rates with CK-based SAPBI to WBI with a smaller rate of radiation-induced toxicities to non-target tissues, such as the heart and lungs.

Between November 2018 and September 2024, in the NIO prospective phase II CK-based SAPBI study overall 92 patients have been treated with early-stage (Stage I-II) low-risk invasive breast cancer after breast-conserving surgery followed by SAPBI using the CK system. Seventy-one patients received 25 Gy in four daily fractions of 6.25 Gy. After a median follow-up of 48 months, no local, regional, or distant recurrence was observed. Side effects were mild, with only grade 1 erythema, oedema, pain, and fibrosis reported. Cosmetic outcomes were excellent-good in most cases. An additional 21 patients have been treated with a different SAPBI regimen of 22.35 Gy in three daily fractions of 7.45 Gy. At a limited follow-up (median 4 months) neither local recurrence nor severe side effect was reported.

These findings confirm the feasibility, tolerability, and effectiveness of CK-based SAPBI, making it a promising alternative to other traditional external beam irradiation techniques for the delivery of APBI.

Keywords: Breast cancer, SBRT, SAPBI, Cosmetic effects

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